

CoSMPAD: Comparative Secretory Microbial Preprotein Activity Database

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ABSTRACT

Protein transport across biological membranes is a highly regulated process that plays critical roles in various biological processes, including the sorting of proteins to organelles or protein secretion into the cellular environment. Signal peptides (SPs) not only direct newly synthesized proteins to the translocation machinery but also exert control over their folding and synthesis rate. From an industrial perspective, protein secretion offers cost-saving advantages compared to intracellular protein production by simplifying downstream purification processes. However, achieving high protein secretion yields is a complex task influenced by multiple factors, including the choice of vector and promoter system, cultivation conditions, codon usage, and precursor protein properties. Consequently, the selection of an optimal SP becomes a trial-and-error process, typically involving semi-rational approaches such as SP-mutagenesis or SP-library screening.

To address this challenge, the Comparative Secretory Microbial Preprotein Activity Database (CoSMPAD) has been developed, consolidating more than 20 types of experimental information obtained from 50 secreted proteins utilizing various SPs. CoSMPAD serves as a comprehensive reference for the recombinant protein research community. It facilitates the development of predictive models that analyze the impact of these factors on protein secretion and can be found at: <https://cosmpad-tbp.streamlit.app/>.

INTRODUCTION

Protein secretion plays a pivotal role in biotechnological processes, facilitating the production and downstream processing of recombinant proteins that are in high demand for various applications. This applies in particular for industrial enzymes and biopharmaceutical proteins, which represent significant markets (1). Microbial systems have gained increasing attention due to their cost-effectiveness and high productivity, making them attractive platforms for protein production (2). Protein production encompasses a diverse array of cellular processes,

including transcription, translation, secretion, chaperone-assisted folding, formation of inclusion bodies, and protein degradation by proteases (3,4). Among these processes, protein secretion stands out as a critical bottleneck that needs to be effectively addressed. Secretion involves the translocation of proteins from the cytoplasm to the extracellular environment, necessitating their passage across one or more cellular membranes. Organisms have evolved a multitude of mechanisms to achieve efficient protein secretion, with the general secretory (Sec) and twin arginine translocation (Tat) pathways being the most prominent (5). The efficiency of protein secretion relies on the properties of SPs which are short peptide sequences located at the N-terminus of precursor proteins. SPs not only direct the newly synthesized proteins to the translocation machinery but also play a role in modulating protein stability, synthesis rate, and folding efficiency (6-8). These peptides, typically consisting of around 30 amino acids, act as molecular labels that guide the protein to its proper destination, with signal peptidases cleaving them during the secretory process (9,10). Despite the availability of various predictors to identify potential SPs (11–14), accurately predicting their efficiency when fused to specific proteins remains challenging.

Consequently, SP selection has become a crucial step in optimizing protein secretion. Two primary approaches are commonly employed: SP-library screening using either natural (15–28) or synthetic SPs (29,30), and SP-mutagenesis (31–34). Nevertheless, multiple factors influence secretion yields in conjunction with these strategies, including the choice of expression host (35,36), medium composition (37–39), promoter selection (41–47), SP-Protein linker design (48,49), and protein properties (15,49–51). Efforts to enhance protein yields extend beyond SP optimization. Genetic features and the secretory machinery elements can be modified to further improve secretion efficiency (23,52–57). Given the complexity and interplay of these factors, the existence of a comprehensive database that encompasses all relevant experimental data is of paramount importance. There is only one database containing the information for some of these factors, namely SPSED (58). Although the SPSED database provides valuable information on some of these factors, CoSMPAD now offers a more comprehensive view, summarizing a broader range of factors affecting protein secretion which are crucial for modelling approaches.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Database Implementation

CoSMPAD is implemented in python using the streamlit open-source app framework (<https://streamlit.io/>).

Data collection

The expression conditions used for the secretion of 50 preproteins from microbial organisms, as reported in 41 different references (15-56) were manually curated and included in the database. DNA sequences were retrieved according to the amino acid sequence given in each reference using GenBank (59). These entries comprise a total of 3716 instances in non-reactor conditions and secretion efficiency was assessed based on extracellular enzyme

Expression System Kit (Takara Bio) was used (19–27). It must be noted that, since some proteins were codon optimized and this data is not available online, the DNA sequences of such proteins were not included in the database.

RESULTS

The CoSMPAD webpage was developed using Streamlit, providing a user-friendly interface for data retrieval. Users can conveniently filter the database by species, host, promoter, protein, SP name, and reference. An interactive dataframe can be optionally displayed throughout the filtering process, ensuring a dynamic and seamless user experience. As shown in Figure 2, the CoSMPAD web interface showcases the database's content and features, including a tutorial to guide users. Furthermore, when applying a filter for a specific protein in a single host, an interactive barplot is generated, illustrating the enzyme activities associated with different SPs. By clicking on a specific bar (representing a SP), users can easily access additional information in Uniprot. This integration enhances the usability and functionality of CoSMPAD, facilitating efficient exploration and analysis of protein secretion data.

Figure 2. CoSMPAD tutorial. Illustrates database fundamentals and the search workflow.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we developed the Comparative Microbial Secretory Preprotein Activity Database (CoSMPAD) as a comprehensive resource for the research community. Our aim was to address the limitations of existing databases and provide helpful insights to facilitate the selection and optimization of SPs for efficient protein secretion. CoSMPAD encompasses a wide range of experimental information obtained from previously published studies on the secretion of 50 proteins utilizing different SPs, making it significantly larger than existing databases such as SPSED (58). However, when this database is used as a benchmark, our database differs in critical points from a modelling and data analysis perspective: i) the SPSED database does not acknowledge linker sequences between SPs and proteins, although current research shows their cruciality for secretion efficiencies (48), ii) SPSED gives no information on the cultivation conditions or expression vector systems that were used to achieve effective protein secretion; iii) only efficient SPs are listed, but not those with low secretion efficiency; iv) our database presents information for 50 proteins and 20 hosts with ~3 times more examples than SPSED.

CoSMPAD serves as a valuable resource for researchers seeking to retrieve comprehensive information on cultivation conditions, promoters, and SPs used in protein secretion. This database empowers researchers to make informed decisions regarding experimental design and the selection of suitable SPs for their protein of interest (POI). Even in cases where a specific protein is not included in the database, CoSMPAD can be utilized as a semi-rational approach for SP selection by considering protein similarity. Moreover, for POIs that lack significant similarity to existing entries, CoSMPAD enables the identification of efficient SPs through the analysis of promiscuous SPs capable of efficiently secreting multiple proteins. Notably, examples such as SP_{aprE} and SP_{estA} have demonstrated their efficacy in secreting 11 and 9 different proteins, respectively. This means that when compared to their respective SP-library they show to have an enzyme activity higher than at least 75% of the SPs tested, particularly when the expression host belongs to the *Bacillus* genus (15-19,54,55).

In conclusion, the development of CoSMPAD fills a significant gap in the field of protein secretion research by providing a comprehensive and curated resource for the selection and optimization of SPs. By considering crucial factors such as linker sequences, cultivation conditions, and expression vector systems, CoSMPAD offers a more realistic representation of the protein secretion process. The availability of predictive and classification models trained using information extracted from amino acid and nucleic acid sequences (30,60-62), highlights the potential for CoSMPAD to serve as a valuable data source for the creation of machine learning models. These advancements have the potential to improve recombinant protein production and drive innovation in diverse biotechnological applications.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The CoSMPAD webserver is available at <https://cosmpad-tbp.streamlit.app/>.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interests.

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